

Emowering Visually Challenged English Language Learners with Technology and Computer Assisted Learning

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Abstract

Undoubtedly, technology devices have been dominating the contemporary world. One of them is a computer. Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) has been employed as a teaching method in English language education across several institutions. It has mitigated learning challenges in many ways. Now more than ever, visually challenged learners have been allowed to actively engage in the learning process. Furthermore, it has afforded these learners the chance to engage confidently in many academic pursuits such as reading, writing, and teaching English, as demonstrated by the concept of 'opportunity to learning in 2009. Furthermore, it allows VCL to enhance their proficiency in all facets of the English language. However, it also has some functional impairments that need to be addressed. This article looks into the need for possessing technical knowledge in the process of English language acquisition among the visually challenged learners.

Keywords: visually challenged learners, English language, language skills, English proficiency, technical knowledge etc.

Introduction

Education is universally accessible. It is anticipated that any form of educational advancement will be universally applicable to all learners, regardless of their degree of education. Technology-assisted learning is a recently developed notion in English teaching. Therefore, the objective of this study is to promote the utilisation of technological tools in English language classrooms by visually challenged learners. In addition, it will guarantee the active involvement of the Engineers in resolving any technological limitations.

English, as a language that offers many opportunities, has not yet been given a suitable place in the curriculum and has not received adequate attention in the classroom. Typically, teachers are unable to give individual attention to every kid in the class. It establishes a divide between the instructor and students. Consequently, the learners encounter difficulties during the learning process. (Johnstone 2009) Particularly, visually challenged learners who are a

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minority at integrated institutions face greater difficulty compared to other learners due to the predominantly visual approach used in the English teaching curriculum. Given that virtual classroom learners now have access to technological assistance, it is reasonable to allow them to utilise Automated Tutoring Systems in English language courses to enhance their proficiency in the English language. Therefore, this study introduces the use of the technology to address the issues and elucidates the methods to enhance the language proficiency of visually challenged. Furthermore, this study will systematically explain the functionality of all currently accessible technical instruments about these learners.

Accessible Technological Tools for VC Learners

Braille, stylus, Braille books, Braille dictionaries, Braille printers, Braille embosser, refreshable Braille displays. The Talking Typer is an Assistive technology that converts text on a screen into audible speech, Speech recognition software, text-to-speech software (TTS), optical character recognition (OCR) software, Braille translation software, and alternate keyboard. Audio players, Electronic books, expansive displays, Closed-circuit television (CCTV), Job access with speech (JAWS), and Non-Visual Desktop Applications (NVDA). There are forty cells. Linguistic lexicons that provide spoken or written definitions, Screen magnifiers and handheld electronic magnifiers Dictation devices and transcriptions, scanners, and standalone reading machines. The VCLS offers various technical equipment such as fusers, swell sheets, pen drive boxes, and angel readers to enhance English language abilities (2015). Several of them are now being utilised. However, numerous devices have been lately altered, allowing for the substitution of the 'scribe system'. (Steer 2010)

Several studies have been conducted in foreign nations on the utilisation of assistive technology (ATS) in English language schools to enhance different parts of the English language. In India, only explanatory papers have been written regarding the functionality of screen readers put on technological devices in connection with VCLS.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the use of Artificial Tutoring Systems in English language classes for Virtual Collaborative Learning Spaces in India, to enhance students' proficiency in the English language. The researcher contends that using visual stimuli in English language classrooms does not aid Visual and Communicative Language Skills in comprehending and enhancing their proficiency in the English language. (Vinoth, 2015)

Several universities have been providing comprehensive training to the students to equip them with the necessary skills to operate technology gadgets. Notable organisations include the Indian Association for the Blind in Madurai, the National Institute for Visually Handicapped in Chennai, the National Institute for the Blind in Delhi and Mumbai, the Tamil Nadu Association for the Blind and the Kamala Venkateshwaran Training Centre in Chennai, and the Madras Resource Centre for the Differently Abled and others.

Various types of screen readers and screen magnifiers aid visually challenged learners in enhancing their familiarity with all areas of the English language. VC learner utilises speech recognition software to run their computer and input data with voice commands, eliminating the need for a mouse or keyboard. Text-to-speech software transforms written text, including text files, web pages, PDFs, and emails, into audio files that are compatible with various devices, such as computers, MP3 players, iPods, and CD players. Job Access with Speech (JAWS) is a software that helps visually impaired individuals to read texts in English as well as 30 other foreign languages (Freedom Scientific, 2016). The Non-Visual Desktop Application can help the VCL (Visual Component Library) to interpret and comprehend written content that is in other languages or dialects. These screen readers have been implemented in select special schools designed for visually challenged learners to enhance their educational engagement.

These screen readers possess the capacity to instruct visually challenged learners in the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Focus on Listening Skills

As VCLs cannot perceive visual stimuli, they typically rely on auditory cues to interpret visual information. Screen readers, unlike manual readers, play a significant role in facilitating the learning process by utilising VCL. They can listen an unlimited number of times. In the realm of visually impaired individuals, heightened attention to listening skills becomes paramount, as they lack the ability to perceive visual stimuli. This reliance on auditory cues shapes their understanding of the surrounding world, emphasizing the significance of effective listening skills in their daily lives.

One crucial tool that enhances the learning experience for visually challenged learners is the screen reader. Unlike traditional manual reading methods, screen readers leverage

technology to audibly convey the content of digital text, providing a bridge between the visual information and the auditory senses of visually challenged learners. This technology not only facilitates access to educational materials but also fosters the development of advanced listening capabilities.

The pivotal role of screen readers lies in their ability to be repetitive without limitations. Visually challenged learners can listen to the same content an unlimited number of times, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the material. This feature not only accommodates various learning paces but also encourages a thorough absorption of information through repetitive auditory exposure. As visually challenged learners engage with content through screen readers, they refine their listening skills in nuanced ways. The auditory processing of information becomes finely tuned, enabling them to discern subtle details, nuances, and tones in spoken language. This heightened sensitivity to auditory cues extends beyond the realm of education, positively impacting their ability to navigate and interact with the broader world. Furthermore, the emphasis on listening skills extends beyond the academic sphere, influencing social interactions and professional environments. Visually challenged individuals often rely on verbal communication and active listening to comprehend and respond effectively. This necessity not only sharpens their ability to grasp spoken information but also cultivates strong interpersonal communication skills.

Thus, the intersection of visual impairment and technological advancements, particularly through screen readers, underscores the critical role of listening skills in the lives of visually challenged individuals. The cultivation of these skills not only enhances educational experiences but also empowers them to navigate various facets of life with heightened sensitivity and adaptability. As society continues to embrace inclusivity, recognizing and understanding the importance of listening skills in the context of visual impairment becomes increasingly essential for fostering a truly accessible and equitable environment.

Focus on Speaking Skills

Empirical evidence supports the notion that learners who have access to technological gadgets possess a greater repertoire of vocabulary compared to their peers. Therefore, their proficiency in speaking surpasses that of typical learners. Screen readers such as JAWS and NVDA, which are created in English-speaking countries, enable visually challenged

individuals to listen to English content. Consequently, their precision and proficiency, along with other subsidiary abilities, will be significantly enhanced. (Mellor 2006) Additionally, it serves as a source of motivation for pupils to actively participate in classroom discussions. Through this method, they will always face challenges in every domain.

Screen readers play a pivotal role in this linguistic enhancement by providing visually impaired learners with the opportunity to listen to English content. The auditory exposure to diverse vocabulary, sentence structures, and language nuances contributes significantly to the precision and proficiency of their spoken communication. As these individuals engage with a variety of content, their language skills are honed, allowing them to articulate thoughts and ideas with a nuanced and refined command of the English language.

This enhancement in speaking proficiency, coupled with the development of other subsidiary abilities, presents a comprehensive skill set for visually challenged learners. The auditory nature of the learning process through screen readers cultivates not only linguistic prowess but also auditory discrimination, intonation, and pronunciation. These refined skills contribute to effective verbal communication, allowing visually challenged individuals to express themselves eloquently and with confidence.

Moreover, the utilization of screen readers serves as a powerful motivator for visually impaired pupils to actively participate in classroom discussions. The technology empowers them to access information independently, fostering a sense of inclusivity and equal participation. The ability to contribute to discussions with a well-developed vocabulary and linguistic fluency enhances their overall academic experience, promoting self-assurance and a positive attitude towards learning.

However, it is crucial to acknowledge that, like any other learning method, the use of screen readers presents its own set of challenges. Visually impaired learners using this technology may encounter difficulties in specific domains, such as interpreting visual content or facing technological barriers. Despite these challenges, the empowerment gained through enhanced speaking skills encourages individuals to confront and overcome obstacles, fostering resilience and adaptability. The symbiotic relationship between access to assistive technologies like screen readers and the development of speaking skills thus is evident. The linguistic enrichment achieved through auditory exposure not only elevates proficiency but also

motivates visually challenged learners to actively engage in academic discourse. While challenges persist, the overall impact of such technological interventions on speaking skills is profound, contributing to a more inclusive and empowering educational experience for visually impaired individuals.

Focus on Reading Skills as a Part of Listening Skills

There exist four types of VCLs. The types of vision impairment include partial, complete, low vision, and legally recognised visual correction lenses (VCLs). Except for the second category, the other three categories are capable of participating in the act of reading to a certain degree. Because sounds and pictures are fundamental components of any language, completely visual programming languages (VCLs) can't comprehend the visual representation of any language. They are unable to comprehend written stuff. Therefore, they utilise the readily available screen readers.

Focus on Writing or Typing Skills

Regarding writing, the Braille method, which is a form of writing that can be felt by touch, has been widely utilised by individuals with visual impairments. Recently, due to various limitations in this approach, it has been substituted by technological devices that empower visually challenged individuals to independently write, type, and make notes. Moreover, this approach has the potential to substitute the traditional method of manual regular scribing to verify the English language proficiency of VC learners.

Drawbacks in the Use of Tehcnology as a Tool for Teaching

Technology, as a tool for teaching, has not yet provided sufficient support for Virtual Collaborative Learning in the acquisition of English language skills. There are several drawbacks, including

One notable limitation hindering the effectiveness of technology in supporting Virtual Collaborative Learning (VCL) for the acquisition of English language skills is the lack of proper document alignment guidance for VCL users. Technical devices often fall short in providing adequate support for visually challenged learners in aligning documents, making it challenging for them to navigate and access content seamlessly. The absence of clear alignment

guidance can lead to difficulties in comprehending the structure and organization of textual information, impeding the learning process.

Another drawback arises from the impact of screen readers on technical devices (TDs). While screen readers are essential tools for visually impaired individuals, their installation on TDs can significantly slow down the overall system performance. This slowdown can impede the smooth functioning of applications and software, creating a less efficient and more frustrating learning experience for VCL users. The reduced speed can hinder the timely completion of tasks, limiting the effectiveness of technology as a teaching tool.

Financial constraints pose another challenge, as screen readers, essential for VCL, often come with a high price tag. The cost of acquiring and maintaining these assistive technologies can be a barrier for many visually challenged learners, limiting their access to the tools necessary for effective language acquisition. The expense associated with screen readers exacerbates existing inequalities in educational opportunities, hindering the potential benefits of technology in language learning for these individuals.

Limited knowledge about technical devices represents yet another obstacle to the integration of technology in VCL for English language acquisition. Some visually challenged learners may lack the necessary understanding of how to operate and maximize the potential of technical devices, impeding their ability to fully engage with educational content. This knowledge gap further highlights the need for comprehensive training and support to ensure that technology is utilized effectively in the learning process.

Furthermore, the exposure to technical devices is often limited for visually challenged learners, particularly in environments where access to such resources is scarce. The lack of exposure hampers the development of essential digital literacy skills, hindering the seamless incorporation of technology into language learning. Without sufficient exposure, visually challenged learners may struggle to adapt to the virtual collaborative nature of language education through technological means.

The performance of text, JPEG, and PDF converters represents another challenge, as these tools often fall short in accurately converting and presenting content for visually challenged learners. Poorly performing converters can compromise the integrity of textual information, leading to misunderstandings and hindering the overall learning experience in a

VCL setting. Lastly, an over-reliance on auto spelling correction, grammar correction, and copy-paste options can be detrimental to the language learning process. Depending too heavily on these features may lead VCL users to prioritize convenience over the development of their language skills. Relying on automated corrections and copying content without thorough engagement may result in a superficial understanding of language constructs, impeding the depth of language acquisition through the chosen pedagogy. Thus, while technology has the potential to revolutionize Virtual Collaborative Learning for visually challenged individuals acquiring English language skills, these drawbacks highlight the importance of addressing technical, financial, and educational challenges to ensure equitable and effective integration of technology in language education.

Conclusion

Visually impaired learners have transformed into learners who receive technical assistance. All VCLs have received comprehensive instruction from specialised educators in dedicated educational institutions. Each of them can independently operate with the aid of screen readers. It would be difficult for someone to take advantage of TD (presumably referring to a specific technology or concept) if they are not familiar with it or have not received sufficient education on the subject. This assumes that the person in question does not have a visual impairment from birth. In addition, there are several aforementioned deficiencies. If those functional limitations were corrected, VCLs would not rely on other learners for any aid. Additionally, they may be granted permission to utilise Assistive Technologies (ATs) within the English language classroom.

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